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МУНДАРИЖА | СОДЕРЖАНИЕ | CONTENT

1. Abdieva Yulduz, Agzamova Gulnara STUDY OF CENTRAL HEMODYNAMICS IN PATIENTS WITH SILICOSIS AND THEIR CORRELATION ANALYSIS WITH MARKERS OF SYSTEMIC INFLAMMATION.....	6
2. Saitnazarov Jamshid, Khaydarov Artur, Kimsanov Shamsiddin, Olimov Azimjon IMPLANTS WITH PARTIAL AND COMPLETE TOOTH LOSS.....	13
3. Irbutaeva Lola, Rasulova Nodira A GENTLE METHOD OF TREATING CHILDREN OF THE FIRST YEAR OF LIFE WITH PERINATAL ENCEPHALOPATHY.....	19
4. Kamilov Haidar, Kamilova Adiba, Rakhimova Raykhon PAIN INTENSITY AND ITS ASSESSMENT IN THE CASE OF GLOSSALGIA.....	23
5. Azizov Abror, Asilova Saodat, Ubaydullaev Bekzod EVALUATION OF THE FUNCTIONAL STATE OF PATIENTS AFTER ARTHROPLASTY WITH ANKYLOSED HIP JOINT.....	28
6. Kamilov Kh.M., Maksudova L.M., Ikramov O.I., Babakhanova D.M., Rustamova K.B. CHOICE OF TREATMENT PATIENTS WITH ENDOPHTHALMITIS.....	39
7. Tulabaeva G.M., Talipova Y.Sh., Sagatova H.M., Abdukadirova N.M., Khusanov A.A. STUDY OF THE HYPOLIPIDEMIC AND ANTI-INFLAMMATORY EFFECTS OF “YANTAK” DECOCTION IN PATIENTS WITH CORONARY HEART DISEASE AGAINST THE BACKGROUND OF STANDARD THERAPY.....	44
8. Nabieva Shokhista Mustafaevna EARLY DIAGNOSIS OF CHANGES IN THE FUNCTIONAL STATE OF THE CARDIOVASCULAR SYSTEM IN NEWBORNS WITH PERINATAL LESIONS OF THE CENTRAL NERVOUS SYSTEM.....	53
9. Kamilov Kh.P., Takhirova K.A., Shokirova F.A. MICROBIOLOGICAL AND IMMUNOLOGICAL FEATURES OF MULTIFORM EXUDATIVE ERYTHEMA OF THE MOUTH.....	60
10. Abdieva Yulduz, Agzamova Gulnara, Mukhlisa Abdullayeva COMPARATIVE CHARACTERISTICS OF LABORATORY MARKERS IN PATIENTS WITH SILICOSIS WITH LOW AND PRESERVED LVEF.....	65

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EARLY DIAGNOSIS OF CHANGES IN THE FUNCTIONAL STATE OF THE CARDIOVASCULAR SYSTEM IN NEWBORNS WITH PERINATAL LESIONS OF THE CENTRAL NERVOUS SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

120 newborns with changes in the functional state of the cardiovascular system with perinatal lesions of the central nervous system were examined. The analysis of clinical syndromes and symptoms, as well as indicators of instrumental studies in newborns in the occurrence and development of changes in the functional state of the cardiovascular system with perinatal damage to the central nervous system showed that functional changes in the cardiovascular system (CS) can further affect the health of the child, and with untimely diagnosis of cardio-vascular maladaptation syndrome, the disease can occur with complicated and the long course of the disease of perinatal encephalopathy.

Keywords: newborns, cardiovascular maladaptation, perinatal encephalopathy.

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РАННЯЯ ДИАГНОСТИКА ИЗМЕНЕНИЙ ФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНОГО СОСТОЯНИЯ СЕРДЕЧНО-СОСУДИСТОЙ СИСТЕМЫ У НОВОРОЖДЕННЫХ С ПЕРИНАТАЛЬНЫМИ ПОРАЖЕНИЯМИ ЦЕНТРАЛЬНОЙ НЕРВНОЙ СИСТЕМЫ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Обследовано 120 новорожденных с изменениями функционального состояния сердечно-сосудистой системы с перинатальными поражениями ЦНС. Анализ клинических синдромов и симптомов, а также показателей инструментальных исследований у новорожденных в возникновении и развитии изменений функционального состояния сердечно-сосудистой системы при перинатальном поражении ЦНС показал, что функциональные изменения сердечно-сосудистой системы (ССС) может в дальнейшем отразиться на здоровье ребенка, а при несвоевременной диагностике синдрома сердечно-сосудистой дезадаптации заболевание может протекать с осложненным и затяжным течением болезни перинатальной энцефалопатией.

Ключевые слова: новорожденные, сердечно-сосудистая дезадаптация, перинатальная энцефалопатия, перинатальном поражении ЦНС, функциональное состояние.

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MARKAZIY ASAB TIZIMINING PERINATAL ZARARLANISHI BILAN YANGI TUG'ILGAN CHAQALOQLARDA YURAK-QON TOMIR TIZIMINING FUNKTSIONAL O'ZGARISHLARNI ERTA TASHXISLASH

ANNOTATSIYA

Markaziy asab tizimining perinatal zararlanishi bilan yurak-qon tomir tizimining funksional holati o'zgartirgan 120 ta yangi tug'ilgan chaqaloq tekshirildi. Klinik sindromlar va simptomlarni tahlil qilish, shuningdek, yangi tug'ilgan chaqaloqlarda markaziy asab tizimining perinatal shikastlanishi bilan yurak-qon tomir tizimining funksional holatidagi o'zgarishlarning paydo bo'lishi va rivojlanishidagi instrumental tadqiqotlar ko'rsatkichlari yurak-qon tomir tizimidagi funksional o'zgarishlarni ko'rsatdi bolaning sog'lig'iga yanada ta'sir qilishi mumkin va yurak-qon tomir buzilish sindromi o'z vaqtida tashxisi qo'yilmasa, kasallik perinatal ensefalopatiya kasalligining murakkab va uzoq davom etishi bilan yuzaga kelishi mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: yangi tug'ilgan chaqaloqlar, yurak-qon tomir dezadaptatsiyasi, perinatal ensefalopatiya, funksional xolat, markaziy asab tizimining perinatal zararlanishi.

Relevance. The high frequency, and at the same time the little-studied cardiac pathology in perinatal central nervous system (CNS) lesions in newborn children, makes it necessary to study the development of the disease in more depth. In order to reduce morbidity and infant mortality, the theoretical and practical significance of studying the relationship between the state of the cardiovascular system (CS) and the central nervous system in perinatal lesions of the central nervous system in newborns is obvious, in order to develop optimally effective diagnostic methods. In recent years, diseases of the cardiovascular system in children have been detected more and more often, among which functional pathology of the heart is of great importance [1].

At the same time, various disorders of the condition in the perinatal period of a newborn can cause the development of cardiovascular disorders, the development of heart failure [2,3,4].

In newborns with perinatal hypoxia, developing hypoxic-ischemic changes in many organs and systems of the body later manifest themselves in the form of myocardial changes, the severity of which depends on the severity of hypoxia, hemodynamic disorders, as well as their pathological interactions with each other [5,6]. The complex of changes that occur in this case has an adverse effect on both the central nervous system, disrupting the regulatory influence of subcortical structures of the brain on the functional state of internal organs, and directly on the cardiovascular system [7,8], which in turn undoubtedly has an adverse effect on the neurological status, thereby creating a "closed" circle. It is known that the development of cardiovascular disorders can be caused by damage to the cerebral regulatory mechanisms of the cardiovascular system [9].

There are insufficient studies on the postnatal adaptation of the cardiovascular system and neonatal hypoxia affected infants, no work has been found on corrective measures in this category of patients [10].

The purpose of the research: to study the functional state of the cardiovascular system in newborns with perinatal damage to the central nervous system to improve the diagnosis of the disease

Material and methods of research. In connection with the above, according to the set goal, 120 newborns with perinatal CNS lesions of moderate and severe severity were studied, who were on inpatient treatment in the department of neonatal pathology and in the department of neonatal resuscitation of the Samarkand Regional Children's Multidisciplinary Medical Center of Samarkand.

According to the set goals and objectives, we conducted examinations of sick children who were divided into groups III: group I consisted of 50 newborns with functional changes in the CS in patients with perinatal CNS lesions of moderate severity. Group II included 40 newborns with functional changes in the CS in patients with severe perinatal CNS lesion. To assess the effectiveness of the diagnostic coefficient, group III included 30 newborns with perinatal CNS lesion. The control group is consisted of 30 healthy newborns.

The results of the research. When analyzing the frequency of occurrence of clinical symptoms of CS disorders in newborns with perinatal CNS damage, in a significant number of newborns with perinatal CNS damage in the presence of CS changes, verification of their diagnosis according to physical examination caused certain difficulties due to the similarity of a number of symptoms. The results of an objective examination of sick children are presented in Table 1 and Figures 1 and 2.

Table 1

Clinical symptoms of CS disorders in newborns with perinatal CNS lesion (frequency in %)

№	Indicator	I group (n=50)		II group (n=40)	
		Абс.	%	Абс.	%
	Marbling of the skin	3	6,0	9	22,5
	Generalized cyanosis	1	2,0	3	7,5
	Acrocyanosis	2	4,0	7	17,5
	Muffled heart tones	4	8,0	16	40,0
	Deafness of heart tones	7	14,0	11	22,5
	Systolic murmur at the top of the heart	8	16,0	19	47,5
	Systolic murmur at the base of the heart	12	24,0	14	35,0
	The accent of the II tone over the pulmonary artery	9	18,0	17	42,5
	Tachycardia	12	24,0	27	67,5
	Bradycardia	9	18,0	12	30,0

It was revealed that, in contrast to group I patients, in group II there was a higher incidence of dyspnea (31.7% and 56.6%, respectively), and its intensification with anxiety.

Figure 1. Frequency of symptoms of CS changes in patients (%).

In this diagram, you can clearly see how the clinical signs of the cardiovascular system changed in newborns in groups I and II, divided depending on the degree of central nervous system

damage (moderate and severe). Marbling of the skin was found in 6.0% of group I newborns, while the occurrence of marbling of the skin was 22.5% in group II; general cyanosis was also less common in group I than in group II (2.0% and 7.5%, respectively); acrocyanosis in group II was much more common than in group I group: 4.0% and 17.5%; tachycardia and bradycardia in group II were detected twice as much as in group I: tachycardia – 24.0% and 67.5%, bradycardia – 18.0% and 30.0% respectively.

It can be concluded that the clinical signs of the cardiovascular system of newborns differ significantly in groups of patients with moderate and severe severity of perinatal central nervous system damage.

Figure 2. Frequency of auscultative changes in the CS in patients.

Auscultative data of the cardiac system revealed significant differences (Figure 2), so muffled heart tones were detected in 8.0% of patients of group I and 40.0% of children of group II, deafness of heart tones in 14.0% and 27.5%, systolic noise at the apex of the heart in 16.0% and 47.5%, systolic noise based on hearts in 24.0% and 35.05%, accent tones over the pulmonary artery in 18.0% and 42.5%, respectively, in groups I and II of newborns.

Table 2.

Dynamics of the disappearance of pathological symptoms from CS in patients (in days)

Symptoms	I group	II group	P
Cyanosis	4,1±0,6	7,3±1,1	<0,01
Deafness of heart tones	3,1±0,4	7,1±1,3	<0,01
Systolic noise	5,1±0,6	7,2±1,0	>0,1
Tachycardia	3,8±0,4	5,5±0,5	<0,01
Bradycardia	2,7±0,2	3,9±0,4	<0,01

Note: P is the reliability of the differences between the groups.

During the study of the dynamics of the disappearance of pathological symptoms from CS in newborns who suffered perinatal CNS lesion, the differences between the groups were significant for cyanosis, which disappeared in group I by 4.1±0.6 days, in group II by 7.3±1.1 days, tone deafness by 3.1±0.4 and 7.1±1.3, tachycardia by 3.8±0.4 and 5.5±0.5, bradycardia by 2.7±0.2 and 3.9±0.4 days, respectively, in the observation groups (P<0.01). The only significant difference between the groups was such a pathological symptom as systolic noise - at 5.1±0.6 and at 7.2±1.0 days (P>0.1).

Table 3

Analysis of heart rate and respiratory rate in patients with perinatal lesions of the central nervous system.

Indicator	I group	II group	P
Heart rate (perminute)	111,4 ±5,3	122,6 ±7,8	<0,05
Respiratoryrate (perminute)	46,4 ±3,2	52,2 ±2,6	<0,05

Note: P is the reliability of the differences between the groups.

The study of CVS in patients showed that in most patients with severe perinatal CNS damage, there were more pronounced CVS disorders in comparison with the group of newborns with an average degree of CNS damage.

Thus, the results of electrocardiographic examination showed (Table 3, Figure 4, that in children of group I, the frequency of occurrence of signs of cardiovascular maladaptation was lower than in patients of group II. According to studies, signs of cardiac maladaptation in perinatal CNS lesions were present in all patients of group II, and there were cases of significant differences in the combination of several electrocardiographic indicators.

Table 4

The frequency of indicators of electrocardiographic examination of newborns with perinatal CNS lesion (%).

	Indicator	I group (n=50)		II group (n=40)	
		Abs.	%	Abs.	%
1	Sinustachycardia	3	6,0	8	20,0
2	Sinusbradycardia	2	4,0	5	12,5
3	Extrasystole	1	2,0	2	5,0
4	Slowing down of intra-ventricular conduction	3	6,0	7	17,5
5	Incomplete blockade of the right leg of the Gis beam	10	20,0	14	35,0
6	Overload of the right ventricle	4	8,0	9	22,5
7	Overload of the left ventricle	3	6,0	7	17,5

Figure 3. Frequency of electrocardiographic examination of newborns with perinatal CNS lesion (%).

The most characteristic clinical signs associated with myocardial ischemia were identified, recorded simultaneously with changes in the ECG. These included: sinus tachycardia was observed in 3 (6.0%) children of group I, while in children of group II sinus tachycardia (heart rate at rest more than 170 beats per 1 min) was recorded 2.5 times more often - in 8 (20.0%), sinus bradycardia (episodes of heart rate less than 90 in 1 min) in 2 (4.0%) children, versus 5 (12.5%), extrasystole was present only in 1 (2.0%) children of group I, versus 2 (5.0%) in children of group II, slowing down inside the ventricular conduction was observed in 3 (6.0%) of group I newborns, 7 (17.5%) of group II newborns, incomplete blockade of the right leg of the Hiss bundle was determined in 10 (20.0%) of group I newborns and in 14 (35.0%) of group II newborns, overload of the right ventricle was determined in 4 (8.0%) of I newborns groups and in 9 (22.5%) newborns of group II, Left

ventricular overload was observed in 3 (6.0%) of group I newborns and in 7 (17.5%) of group II newborns.

The results of the main quantitative indicators of the neurosonographic study of the brain in newborns show changes characteristic of perinatal brain damage in all studied parameters (Table 5)

Table 5

Characteristics of quantitative indicators of neurosonographic examination of newborns with perinatal CNS lesion.

№	Indicators (ml)	I group (n=50)	II group (n=40)
1	Thirdventricle	4,6±0,2	5,9±0,4
2	Fourthventricle	5,1±0,3	6,1±0,5
3	Subarachnoidspace	3,9±0,2	4,9±0,4

Note: P is thereliabilityofthedifferencesbetweengroups I and II.

Thus, an increase in the size of the third and fourth ventricles, subarachnoid space in group I was revealed to 4.6±0.2, 5.1±0.3 and 3.9±0.2, and in group II to 5.9±0.4, 6.1±0.5 and 4.9±0.4 ml. ml, respectively.

The main instrumental indicators that objectively reflect the state of the CCC during perinatal changes in the central nervous system are shown in Table 6 and Figure 4.

Table 6

Characteristics of Echocardiography indicators in examined newborns with perinatal CNS lesion.

№	Groupsofchildren	I group	II group
1	Final systolic size, cm	0,93±0,04	0,85±0,11
2	Final systolic volume, cm	3,24±0,34	3,14±0,23
3	Final diastolic size, cm	1,50±0,21	1,48±0,33
4	Final diastolic volume, ml	7,63±1,26	6,58±1,47
5	Impact volume, ml	5,14±0,68	5,09±0,74

Note: P is the reliability of the differences between the groups.

Figure 4

Indicators of Echocardiography indicators studies in children.

Table 6 and Figure 4 indicate that with this pathology, only the shock volume clearly goes beyond the age norm, which indicates a good adaptive ability in this age period.

Conclusions.

Thus, the analysis of clinical syndromes and symptoms, as well as indicators of instrumental studies shows that in newborns with perinatal CNS lesion, functional changes in the Cardiovascular system may further affect the child's health, and with untimely diagnosis of cardiovascular maladaptation syndrome, the disease may occur with a complicated and prolonged course of the disease of perinatal encephalopathy.

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ЎЗБЕК ТИББИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

4 ЖИЛД, 3 СОН

ЎЗБЕКСКИЙ МЕДИЦИНСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ

ТОМ 4, НОМЕР 3

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